

FAILURE BEHAVIOUR OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES UNDER ANTICLASTIC BENDING

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ABSTRACT

In this study, failure behaviour of laminated composite plates subjected to anticlastic bending is investigated. Anticlastic bending is a special case of bi-axial out-of-plane loading that applies predominantly twisting moment. A unique test fixture is designed to achieve anticlastic loading condition. Carbon-fibre-reinforced epoxy is selected as the material of the specimens. Totally nine different layup configurations are chosen and at least four specimens are tested for each configuration. Acoustic emission monitoring (AEM) is utilized to detect the first-ply-failure load and the progressive failure behaviour of the laminates. In this method, sound signals resulting from initiation and progression of damage within the material are detected, and then the signal data are processed to identify the failure modes and determine their time of occurrence. An energy-based method is employed to detect the first-ply-failure. The time of the first signal that yields the peak energy is considered as the first-ply failure initiation time. An FE model is developed to simulate the anticlastic bending test. A code is developed using ANSYS parametric design language to obtain the first-ply-failure predictions using maximum stress, maximum strain, Tsai-Wu, Tsai-Hill, Hashin, Hoffman, and quadric surfaces failure criteria. The experimental and numerical results are then compared. Relative strengths and weaknesses of the failure criteria in estimating failure of laminated composite plates under anticlastic bending are discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Laminated composite plates exhibit much more complex behaviour than the conventional materials. Interactions between fibres and matrix, existence of different failure modes like delamination, fibre breakage, matrix cracking, buckling of fibres, debonding of fibres from matrix, predominance of a different failure mode over the others under a different loading state or a different layup pose great difficulty in predicting their failure behaviour .

In industrial applications, designers face the difficulty of developing safe and optimal designs for composite parts under complex loading cases. So understanding and predicting the failure behaviour of the material under different loading conditions gains importance. Failure mechanisms and response of laminated plates are extensively studied and validity of the failure criteria is investigated for in-plane loading conditions [1-5]. On the other hand, not sufficient attention has been given to out-of-plane loading. Many composite structural parts like aircraft wings and wind turbine blades are subjected to a combination of bending and twisting moments or transverse forces. Failure analyses of composites based on failure criteria validated only for in-plane loading cannot be considered to be reliable, if the part is subjected to out-of-plane loads. Hence, reliable design of laminated composite parts requires use of failure theories validated for various loading conditions.

In the literature, there are a number of studies that examined the failure behaviour of laminated composite under various out-of-plane loads and investigated the validity of different failure criteria. Hara et al. [6] combined experimental and FEA procedures with Weibull statistics and compared the out-of-plane strengths of carbon-fibre-reinforced plastics (CFRP) under direct loading and three-point

bending. Feraboli and Kedward [7] investigated the flexural and interlaminar shear strength of the unidirectional and multi-directional CFRP's using four-point bending. Meng et al. [8] investigated the effect of fibre lay-up on the damage initiation under three-point bending. They compared the test results with the results of a 3D FEA model and an analytical model.

In the literature, usually four-point-bending [7] or three-point-bending [6] tests were conducted to study the out-of-plane failure behaviour of composites. In these tests, specimens were predominantly subjected to uniaxial bending, M_{xx} or M_{yy} . In the tests where transverse loads were applied, specimens were predominantly subjected to bi-axial bending (both M_{xx} or M_{yy}) as seen in Figure 1.a. On the other hand, in anticlastic loading, specimen is predominantly subjected to twisting moment, M_{xy} . This loading state is realized either by applying bending moments in opposite sense (Figure 1.b) or by applying force couples having the same magnitude but opposite direction to the neighbouring corners of a square plate as shown in Figure 1.c. Farsad et al. [9] used anticlastic bending to determine the shear modulus and Poisson's ratio of some polymers and foams. In another research, Farshad [10] investigated the mode III fracture toughness of various materials including CFRP and GFRP by means of anticlastic bending. Makeev et al. [11] used anti-clastic bending to assess the shear stress-strain curves in all three principal planes with a single experiment. Podczeck [12] used this method to determine the fracture properties of some pharmaceutical materials. However, anticlastic bending has not been used to investigate the static failure behaviour of composite materials.

Figure 1. a) Biaxial bending applied by two bending moments in the same sense; b) Anticlastic bending applied by two bending moments in opposite sense; c) Anticlastic bending applied by force couples; d) Bottom portion of the anticlastic test setup developed in this study.

In this study, the strength of continuous fibre-reinforced laminated composite plates with different stacking sequences are investigated under anticlastic bending and validity of selected failure criteria is examined under this loading state. For this purpose, a unique anticlastic bending test apparatus is designed (Figure 1.d). Laminated plates with 100 mm \times 100 mm dimensions and 12-ply thickness are manufactured. The progressive failure behaviour of the specimens is monitored and failure modes are detected during testing by means of acoustic emission monitoring (AEM). In this method, sounds resulting from initiation and progression of damage within the material are detected, and then the signal data are processed to identify the failure modes and determine their time of occurrence. An energy-based method is employed to detect the first-ply-failure. The time of the first signal that yields

the peak energy is considered as the first-ply failure initiation time. The test is simulated by developing a finite element model in ANSYS and a code is developed using ANSYS parametric design language (APDL) to employ the selected failure criteria, which are maximum stress, maximum strain, Tsai-Hill, Tsai-Wu, Hofmann, Hashin, and quadric surfaces. The experimental results and predictions of the failure criteria are compared and the criteria which yield the most realistic results are determined for each stacking sequence. In this way, the validity of the chosen failure criteria is investigated for this type of loading condition and valuable information is provided for the designers as to the reliability of their failure analyses.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Experimental set-up

As depicted in Figure 1.d, specimens are placed on two spherical steel supports, which hold the specimen at points on the diagonal close to the corners. Support points are 15 mm away from the intersecting edges and $15\sqrt{2}$ mm away from the corners. Pin supports are fixed to the bottom portion of the set up to ensure proper alignment of the specimens during testing. The prismatic supports are placed on a sliding base to accommodate different specimen sizes.

2.2 Specimen Preparation

Composite plates are manufactured from AS4/8552 unidirectional composite prepregs. Firstly, prepregs are laid up on a steel tool with desired stacking sequence and thickness, and then they are consolidated and cured in autoclave according to the manufacturer's recommended curing cycle [13]. The cured plates are cut into the shape of a square with 100 mm-length edges. In order to observe how successfully the failure criteria predict the failure trend, i.e. the change in the failure load with a change in the orientation angle, θ , unidirectional $[\theta]_{12}$, and symmetric-balanced, $[(\theta/-\theta)]_3$, layup configurations are chosen, which are $[0]_{12}$, $[5]_{12}$, $[15]_{12}$, $[30]_{12}$, $[45]_{12}$ and $[(5/-5)]_3$, $[(15/-15)]_3$, $[(30/-30)]_3$, $[(45/-45)]_3$. Note that due to the symmetry in geometry and loading, $[\theta]_{12}$ and $[(90^\circ-\theta)]_{12}$ configurations or $[(\theta/-\theta)]_3$ and $[(90^\circ-\theta/90^\circ-\theta)]_3$ configurations yield the same result. Additionally, cross-ply configurations, $[(90/0)]_3$ and $[90_3/0_3]$, are chosen. At least four specimens are tested for each configuration. The thickness of one ply is 0,184 mm according to the product catalogue. In testing some configurations, first-ply failure is observed to occur due to delamination rather than due to an intralaminar failure mode. Considering that in this study, the objective is to examine validity of intralaminar failure criteria, reinforcing strips with 20-mm width are bonded to the edges of the specimens as shown schematically in Figure 2 to reduce the delamination risk at the edges. The centre of the circles in the figure indicates the loading points.

Figure 2. Schematic of orientation angle and loading points of the laminate.

2.3 Experimental Procedure

2.3.1 Tension Tests

Because the matrix properties govern the strength and stiffness of the composites in the transverse direction, which in turn determine the first-ply failure strength of multi-directional laminates, transverse strength deserves a special attention. For this reason, instead of using the catalogue value, the transverse strength of the composite material was determined through tension tests according to ASTM D3039 standards [14].

2.3.2 Anticlastic Bending Tests

Anticlastic bending tests are performed on MTS servo-hydraulic test machine using the anticlastic bending fixture (Figure 3). Tests are performed by controlling displacement. Bottom part of the anticlastic fixture is attached to the piston, which is moving upward with a speed of 1.8 mm/min. Rubber bands are placed between the balls and the specimen to reduce stress concentration at the points of application of loads.

Figure 3. The test apparatus and AE sensors

2.3.3 Acoustic Emission Monitoring

Usually, it is difficult to experimentally determine the first-ply failure load of composite materials unless the first and final-failure loads are the same. This is because initiation of damage usually does not result in a significant change in the macro behaviour of composites. AEM provides a powerful tool for detecting the first-ply failure, progression of failure, and even the failure mode. AEM is capable of discriminating different failure modes by detecting different acoustic signals produced by specimens due to activation of different failure mechanisms. Basic failure mechanisms in laminated composite materials are matrix cracking, fibre-matrix debonding, delamination, fibre buckling, and fibre breakage. Each failure mode generates its characteristic AE signal.

In order to detect sound waves, two piezoelectric transducers are symmetrically placed on the specimen (Figure 3). In order to prevent sliding of the transducers during testing, which may produce noise signals, they are secured by means of elastic bands and tapes. For smooth transmission of sound waves, ultrasonic gel is used as couplant. After cleaning the specimen surface, the gel is applied to the transducer surfaces.

Piezoelectric sensors have an operating frequency range of 150-450 kHz. All signals coming from the transducers are recorded as hit data. Acoustic emission system produces signals characterized by seven AE features; Amplitude, rise time, counts, duration, energy, absolute energy, signal strength. In addition to these features, an important feature is the peak frequency content. The peak frequency of a signal can provide important information about failure mode of the material. However peak frequency

content of each hit cannot readily be obtained from the data. Post-processing is required to obtain peak frequency values for each hit. Because there are numerous AE hits per test, more than 5000 hits for some tests, a macro code is written in Visual Basic Language embedded in MS Excel to calculate the peak frequency values from the waveform of each hit.

2.3.4 Determination of First-Ply-Failure Load

Frequency content of AE hit data provides information about the failure mode. This method is based on classifying the frequency ranges according to the corresponding failure mechanism. The sequence of frequency ranges matched for different failure modes by Gutkin et al. [15] are shown in Figure 4. In this study, this classification is used to interpret AE signals to decide on which failure mechanism may have activated if a particular AE datum is detected. However, additional experiments are also conducted to identify failure modes from AE data. In order to pick the first-ply-failure point, the method proposed by Kam and Lai [16], which is based on the released energy in a similar graphite/epoxy (T300/2500) composite is employed to obtain the peak frequency values.

Figure 4. Classification of failure modes according to their peak frequencies [15].

The bonded reinforcing strips may crack and debond from the specimen surface during the test. Because all these noises are recorded by the AEM device, they need to be identified and eliminated in order to distinguish the hit data related to failure of the specimen itself. In order to discriminate the sounds coming from the specimen and the ones coming from the bonding surface of the reinforcing strips, the peak frequency contents of the hits are examined both for stripped and non-stripped specimen. The peak frequency range of the emissions of strip- specimen bonding surface is found to be between 110-170 kHz. However, the frequency for matrix cracking is observed to be between 130-160 kHz in tensile tests of pure epoxy. During the tensile testing of dog-bone pure epoxy specimens, only the frequency values between 130-160 kHz are obtained. Therefore, the frequency values between 110-130 kHz are assumed to result from strip-specimen debonding.

3 FINITE ELEMENTS ANALYSES (FEA)

A finite element model is developed to simulate the anticlastic bending test and determine the stress and strain states within the specimen using commercial FEA analysis program ANSYS. A code is developed in ANSYS Parametric Design Language (APDL) to implement the failure criteria and predict the first-ply-failure load.

SOLID185, a layered 3-D structural solid element defined by eight nodes, is used to mesh the structural volume (Figure 5). The element has three degrees of freedom at each node.

Because the tests are conducted under displacement control, displacement boundary conditions are defined in the FE model. The two nodes on the same diagonal are held in the same position in the transverse (z -) direction. In order to prevent rigid body motion in other degrees of freedom, three nodes are selected close to the middle of the specimen and they are held in the x and y directions. A value for the transverse displacement is assigned to the other two diagonal nodes such that the maximum failure index becomes equal to 1.0. This value is iteratively found using the secant algorithm. Then, the corresponding stress and strain states, the deflections, the reaction forces, i.e. the failure load, are extracted from the FE results.

Maximum stress, maximum strain, Tsai-Wu, Tsai-Hill, Hoffman, Hashin, and quadric surfaces failure criteria are used to predict the failure load and the corresponding deflection. Among these

criteria, the first three criteria are defined in Ansys software; the rest is implemented by the code.

Figure 5. The meshed structure of the specimen

Laminated CFRP specimens are considered as a whole part with the edge strips. Because concentrated forces and sharp edges in the FE model cause stress concentrations severer than the actual case; these regions are not considered in the failure analysis. Convergence analyses are performed to determine the optimum mesh size. Three different element sizes, 1 mm, 2 mm, and 4 mm, are tried, and the differences in the results indicate that that the suitable mesh size is 2 mm.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Experimental Results

Load & energy vs. displacement and frequency & energy vs. displacement graphs of chosen unidirectional configurations are shown in Figure 6. The hit signal caused the first-ply failure and the corresponding frequencies are indicated on the energy graphs.

Figure 6 Load & energy vs. displacement and frequency & energy vs. displacement graphs of chosen unidirectional configurations.

As can be noticed in the graphs, for some configurations like $[0]_{12}$ and $[30]_{12}$, some energy peaks exist before the detected peak associated with failure. There are three reasons that those peaks are not considered as failure-related peaks. First, they may not correspond to the frequency range under interest; for example in $[0]_{12}$ configuration, the peak that occurs at 8.3-mm deflection has 24 kHz frequency, which may indicate minor matrix cracking. Second, they may not initiate a peak-intensive period as in $[30]_{12}$ and $[45]_{12}$ configurations. That means intensity of the detected signals does not significantly increase after the detection of the first peak. Third, they may be in the frequency range associated with the edge strip-specimen surface debonding as in $[30]_{12}$ configuration. No significant energy peaks are detected during the testing of non-stripped unidirectional specimens before the final catastrophic failure. For this reason, the peaks detected in stripped specimens before the catastrophic failure are attributed to damages in the reinforcing strips. The peak frequency values for the stripped specimens with layups $[0]_{12}$, $[30]_{12}$, and $[45]_{12}$ are 93 kHz, 239 kHz, and 132 kHz, respectively. These values correspond to different failure modes in the studies of Gutkin et al. [15] and De Groot et al. [17]. For example, 93 kHz and 132 kHz correspond to matrix cracking in the study of De Groot et al. [17]. On the other hand, these values correspond to delamination in the study of Gutkin et al. [15]. This discrepancy might have arisen due to the frequency range of sensors used during the tests. The range of the sensors used in the current study is close to the range of the sensors used in the study of De Groot et al. Therefore it can be said that first-ply failure of $[0]_{12}$, $[30]_{12}$, and $[45]_{12}$ are matrix cracking, debonding, and matrix cracking, respectively.

The experimental results for cross-ply laminates are shown in Figure 7. AE energy with 151 kHz frequency is the sign of matrix crack but it does not cause a considerable decrease in the load vs. displacement curve. But when the hit with 253 kHz is obtained, a decrease in the slope begins; besides, frequency clusters around 250 kHz and 350 kHz appear. So, the activated failure mode with frequency values around 250 kHz is believed to represent fibre-matrix debonding.

Figure 7. Load & energy vs. displacement and frequency & energy vs. displacement graphs of cross-ply laminates.

Figure 8. Load & energy vs. displacement and frequency & energy vs. displacement graphs of chosen symmetric-balanced configurations.

The breaking points in load-displacement curves, which indicate sudden drops in stiffness, especially encountered in symmetric-balanced laminates (Figure 8) are not strictly associated with failure. These breaking points may result from slipping between the specimen and the tool or edge

strip-specimen debonding. They do not correspond to significant energy peaks detected by the AE equipment. When the plate with layup $[(5/-5)_3]_s$ is displaced by 12.5 mm, clusters of data are recorded with different frequency ranges but non-observable energy values. With the hit at 136 kHz, frequency values around 185 kHz and with 234 kHz hit, the dots indicating frequency values around 350 kHz appear with high density. So, this hit can be considered as the sign of first-ply failure, since all failure modes are activated and a sudden drop in load is observed in macro level. Also, the frequency values around 350 kHz are the sign of fibre failure. In some cases, first-ply failure is detected at levels where there is no discontinuity or a changing pattern in the load - deflection curve as in $[(30/-30)_3]_s$, and $[(45/-45)_3]_s$ configurations. In some cases like unidirectional laminates, after the first-ply failure, load carrying capacity significantly degrades, while in some other cases like $[(30/-30)_3]_s$ and $[(45/-45)_3]_s$ ultimate strength is significantly higher than the first-ply failure load level. According to above discussion, it can be said that first-ply failure of $[(5/-5)_3]_s$, $[(30/-30)_3]_s$, and $[(45/-45)_3]_s$ are fibre-matrix debonding. For $[(30/-30)_3]_s$ configuration, a decrease in the slope of load vs. displacement curve can be observed after the detection of signal considered as indicating the first-ply failure level at 14-mm displacement.

3.2 Comparison of the Numerical and Experimental Results

3.2.1 Unidirectional laminates, $[\theta]_{12}$

Unidirectional laminates are expected to undergo brittle failure. Occurrence of a brittle catastrophic failure allows one to determine the failure load without performing any acoustic emission monitoring; but AE data are obtained in the present study during testing of the unidirectional specimens to identify and distinguish the emissions coming from edge strip-specimen surface cracks.

Figure 9 shows a comparison of the experimentally determined failure loads of unidirectional laminated plates, $[\theta]_{12}$, and the predictions obtained using the selected failure criteria. As seen in the figure, the maximum stress and maximum strain criteria predict a different trend from that of the others in the first 10 degrees of the fibre orientation angle, θ . At larger angles, predicted load levels become similar and after 20° the criteria estimate about the same levels for the failure loads.

Figure 9. Failure load vs. orientation angle, θ , graph for unidirectional laminates $[\theta]_{12}$.

Table 1 presents the experimental results of the failure loads for the unidirectional specimens and the percentage errors in the predictions of the failure criteria. As seen in the tables, the largest discrepancies between the experimental results and the predictions occur for $[0]_{12}$ and $[5]_{12}$ configurations. Among the failure criteria, the maximum stress and maximum strain criteria yield the worst predictions with an error up to 43,2 %. The quadratic surfaces criterion returns a relatively good prediction with 20,4 % error. Except maximum stress and maximum strain, the failure criteria predict

a decreasing trend for the strength with the increase in the orientation angle, θ . Experiments indicate, however, a decrease in strength for $\theta = 5^\circ$, then increase at 15° , after that a continuous decrease until $\theta = 45^\circ$. However the scatter in the experiments is large for unidirectional specimens. This may be attributed to the sensitivity of the matrix dominated transverse strength to manufacturing defects, which has much more bearing on unidirectional laminates.

Layup	Measured results (N)	Max. Stress	Max. Strain	Tsai-Hill	Tsai-Wu	Hoffman	Hashin	Quadric Surfaces
[0 ₁₂]	660	34.7%	34.7%	29.6%	23.8%	29.6%	23.2%	20.4%
[5 ₁₂]	540	42.6%	43.3%	22.1%	27.5%	21.9%	27.4%	18.7%
[15 ₁₂]	640	-3.9%	-5.6%	-11.9%	-17.2%	-11.9%	-16.5%	-22.2%
[30 ₁₂]	510	-10.6%	-13.1%	-11.1%	-13.6%	-11.0%	-12.3%	-14.4%
[45 ₁₂]	480	-8.3%	-9.9%	-9.0%	-10.7%	-8.9%	-9.9%	12.56%

Table 1. Average values of the experimental results and percentages of error in the predictions of the failure criteria for failure loads of unidirectional specimens, [0₁₂].

3.2.2 Symmetric-Balanced Laminates, [(θ/-θ)₃]_s

Figure 10 shows a comparison of the experimentally determined failure loads of symmetric-balanced specimens, [(θ/-θ)₃]_s, and the predictions obtained using the selected failure criteria. Table 2 presents the experimental results and the percentage errors in the predictions of the selected failure criteria. According to the experiments, strength of the material decreases up to $\theta = 5^\circ$ and then increases continuously. The highest strength is obtained for [(45/-45)₃]_s laminates, while [(5/-5)₃]_s has the lowest strength. The scatter in the experimental results is lower compared to the unidirectional specimen results. Except for the maximum stress and maximum strain criteria, the failure criteria correctly estimate the failure trend; i.e. its decrease up to $\theta = 5^\circ$ and then increase. However, they overestimate the strength for $\theta = 5^\circ$ and $\theta = 15^\circ$

Figure 10. Failure load vs. orientation angle, θ , graph for symmetric-balanced laminates [(θ/-θ)₃]_s.

Layup	Measured results (N)	Max. Stress	Max. Strain	Tsai-Hill	Tsai-Wu	Hoffman	Hashin	Quadric Surfaces
[(5/-5) ₃] _s	580	46.17%	48.69%	28.23%	35.16%	28.90%	35.20%	26.40%
[(15/-15) ₃] _s	1100	2.63%	-1.28%	-13.08%	-3.37%	-11.74%	-2.52%	-17.69%
[(30/-30) ₃] _s	1360	5.83%	-2.87%	5.97%	-4.93	8.27%	0.60%	-2.31%
[(45/-45) ₃] _s	1780	3.82%	-9.88%	-3.04%	-7.20%	0.78%	-2.17%	-6.33%

Table 2. Average values of the experimental results and percentages of error in the predictions of the failure criteria for failure loads of symmetric-balanced specimens, [(θ/-θ)₃]_s.

3.2.3 Other Layup Configurations

Laminates having $[(90/0)_3]_s$ and $[90_3/0_3]_s$ layup sequences are also tested. The experimental results and percentages of error in the predictions are tabulated in Table 3. Experiments show that the first-ply failure strength of $[(90/0)_3]_s$ laminate is slightly higher than that of $[90_3/0_3]_s$ laminate in contrast to the predictions of the criteria. However, the ultimate strength of $[(90/0)_3]_s$ laminate is found to be much higher.

Layup	Measured results (N)	Max. Stress	Max. Strain	Tsai-Hill	Tsai-Wu	Hoffman	Hashin	Quadric Surfaces
$[(90/0)_3]_s$	1080	12.29%	20.14%	12.30%	12.29%	12.27%	12.27%	10.53%
$[0_3/90_3]_s$	1178	18.85%	26.11%	17.87%	18.85%	17.65%	18.84%	16.43%

Table 3. Average values of the experimental results and percentages of error in the predictions of the failure criteria for for cross-ply laminates.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, failure behaviour of laminated composite plates made of AS4/8552 preregs under anticlastic bending is investigated. First-ply failure load is determined by using acoustic emission monitoring (AEM). Reinforcing strips are glued to the edges of the specimens to avoid premature failure by delamination. An energy-based method is employed to detect the first-ply-failure. The time of the first signal which yields the peak energy is considered as the first-ply failure initiation time. Using the time vs. load diagram obtained from the test machine, the corresponding failure load is found. The frequency of the detected signal for the initiation of the failure is generally between 200 kHz and 300 kHz. The sequence of frequency ranges for each failure mode is consistent with reference [15]. However due to different sensors, the values shifted. Frequency values between 170 – 220 kHz are due to delamination and 220 – 270 kHz corresponds to fibre-matrix debonding failure mechanism. First detected first-ply failure mode is an intralaminar failure mode (matrix failure or fibre-matrix debonding), but not delamination.

A finite element model is developed to carry out the structural analysis of the specimen under anticlastic bending. Selected failure criteria are then employed to predict the failure load. The predictions of the failure criteria generally show a good agreement with the experimental results for the symmetric balanced, cross-ply, and the other selected multi-directional configurations. But for unidirectional cases, especially for $[0_{12}]$ and $[5_{12}]$ configurations, predictions show larger discrepancies. They all overestimate the strengths of $[0_{12}]$ and $[5_{12}]$ configurations by 23% to 43%. There are also differences in predicted failure trends for unidirectional laminates $[0_{12}]$. Maximum stress and maximum strain criteria predict the strength of $[5_{12}]$ higher than that of $[0_{12}]$, while the others predict the highest strength for $[0_{12}]$, then continuously decreasing strength up to 45°. The latter trend conforms to the experimental results better. For unidirectional laminates, the best correlation is obtained with Tsai-Wu, Hashin, and quadric surfaces criteria. For symmetric balanced laminates, $[(\theta/-\theta)_3]_s$, maximum stress and maximum strain estimate increased strength for $[3_{12}]$ and $[6_{12}]$, while the others estimate first a decrease, after that continuous increase up to 45°. The experiments support the latter predicted trend. Hashin criterion shows the best correlation in general for symmetric balanced laminates. But for low-angle configurations like $[0_{12}]$ and $[(5/-5)_3]_s$, quadric surfaces criterion performs better for either unidirectional or symmetric-balanced configurations.

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